

A Comprehensive Review on Valuable Components in Food Processing Waste and Their Recovery by Microwave Assisted Extraction

Gıda İşleme Atıklarındaki Değerli Bileşenler ve Mikrodalga Destekli Ekstraksiyon ile Bunların Geri Kazanımları Üzerine Kapsamlı Bir Derleme

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ABSTRACT

In the food industry, huge amounts of waste or by-products are generated during the processing of them. Reutilizing and reducing food waste is essential for both environmental concerns and food security. Food wastes are generally rich in components that can be converted into valuable bioproducts such as bioactive compounds, natural pigments, biochemicals, enzymes, and biofuels. Extraction of these compounds from the waste is a common practice to gain them. In this respect, microwave-assisted extraction (MASE) has been addressed as an efficient and environmentally friendly method compared to traditional ones due to its rapid volumetric heating ability. When MASE is operated in a closed vessel it helps to reach a higher temperature than the boiling point of the solvent and accelerates the mass transfer. Therefore, even components that are difficult to extract can be easily extracted in a few minutes. The present review compiles the potential valuable components present in food waste and gives a brief theoretical background on the fundamentals of microwave heating. It also summarizes recent studies on microwave-assisted extraction of valuable components from food waste. The impact of MASE on the quality attributes of extract, as well as the benefits in terms of processing parameters are discussed. The information presented in the review will assist food processors in choosing the appropriate extraction methods during the food waste valorization.

Keywords: Food waste, microwave assisted extraction, by-products, value-added components

ÖZET

Gıda endüstrisinde, gıda işleme sırasında büyük miktarda atık ya da yan ürünler ortaya çıkmaktadır. Gıda atıklarının yeniden kullanılması ve azaltılması hem çevre hem de gıda güvenliği için oldukça önemlidir. Gıda atıkları genellikle biyoaktif bileşikler, doğal pigmentler, biyokimyasallar, enzimler ve biyoyakıtlar gibi değerli ürünlere dönüştürülebilen bileşenler bakımından zengindir. Bu bileşiklerin atıklardan ekstraksiyonu, bu değerli bileşenleri elde etmek için yaygın bir uygulamadır. Bu bağlamda mikrodalga destekli ekstraksiyon (MASE), hızlı hacimsel ısıtma özelliğinden dolayı geleneksel yöntemlere göre verimli ve çevre dostu bir ekstraksiyon yöntemi olarak ele alınmaktadır. MASE kapalı bir kaptaki çalıştırıldığında, çözücünün kaynama noktasından daha yüksek bir sıcaklığa ulaşmasını sağlayarak kütle transferini hızlandırmaktadır. Bu nedenle, elde edilmesi zor bileşenler bile birkaç dakika içinde kolayca ekstrakte edilebilmektedir. Bu derleme, gıda atıklarında bulunan

katma değerli bileşenler ve mikrodalga ısıtmanın temelleri hakkında kısa bir teorik bilgi sunmaktadır. Ayrıca, mikrodalga destekli ekstraksiyonu ile gıda atıklarından elde edilen değerli bileşenler üzerine yapılan son çalışmaları da özetlemektedir. MASE'nin ekstraktın kalite özellikleri üzerindeki etkisinin yanı sıra işlem parametreleri açısından faydaları tartışılmaktadır. Derlemede sunulan bilgiler, gıda atıklarının değerlendirilmesi sırasında uygun ekstraksiyon yöntemlerini seçmede gıda işleyicilerine yardımcı olacaktır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Gıda atığı, mikrodalga destekli ekstraksiyon, yan ürünler, katma değerli bileşenler

1. INTRODUCTION

Food waste and losses occur during harvesting, production, transportation and consumption stage of food chain. Huge amount of liquid, solid or semi solid waste consisting mainly pomace, peel, cut pieces, seed etc are generated in food processing line due to FAO in 2011 reported that about 1.3 million of the world's food was lost before even reaching the market (FAO (2011)). Valorization of food waste in necessity not only to ensure food security but also for environmental and economical concerns.

Food waste coming from different food sectors is in different constituents and forms. For instance, fruits and vegetable waste are rich in bioactive compounds such as antioxidants, phenolic acids, flavonoids, carotenoids, pectin, etc. On the other hand, animal-origin by-products are rich in collagen, natural pigments, omega fatty acids, chitin, chitosan, proteins, peptides, and calcium. Grain processing wastes are rich in pectin, proteins, citric acid, fibers, cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. These valuable components can be recovered to be used in the food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industry.

Therefore, green and effective methods should be developed to recover bioactive components from food wastes. Among the various extraction technologies, microwave assisted solvent extraction (MASE) stands out with its superior features, especially with its short processing time. MASE provides an effective extraction by rapid heating the extraction solvent and/or sample to high temperatures. Therefore, MASE provides energy savings, low solvent requirements and high productivity compared to traditional heating methods.

The performance of MASE depends on several parameters like sample matrix, its chemical structure and process parameters including solvent, pressure, time and temperature (Azmir, et al. 2013). MASE has recently been successfully used for extraction of phenolic compounds from tea residues (Tsubaki, et al. 2010), pectin from orange peel (Maran, et al. 2013), carotenoid from carrot processing waste (Elik, et al. 2020), gelatin from duck skin (Kim, et al. 2020), fermentable sugar from canola straw (Agu, et al. 2017), and oligosaccharides from lotus seed (Lu, et al. 2017).

The present study aimed to provide a review on valuable components present in food waste, give a brief theoretical knowledge on MASE and to summarize recent developments on extraction of valuable compounds from food industry waste.

2. VALUABLE COMPONENTS in FOOD WASTE

Food waste consists of valuable components resulting along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses. Food waste or by-products from different food sectors can be categorized into two groups of plant and animal origin. The plant originated wastes are generally rich in carbohydrates, protein, fat, vitamin and bioactive components whereas proteins, minerals,

(Ikram-Ul-Haq, et al. 2012), and polyphenol oxidase (Niphadkar and Rathod 2015). Sweet potato residues from starch production can be used to extract the pectin (Zhang, et al. 2013). From the cassava flour production processes, peel and husk are formed as cassava residues. Cassava bagasse revealed during the sieving or straining stage, has been utilized as a sole carbon source to produce fumaric acid by *Rhizopus* strains (Osorio, et al. 2021).

Vegetables and fruits

According to FAO (FAO 2021), vegetable production was 1 billion 89 million tons in 2018 whereas fruits production reached 868 million in the world, inevitably leads to large amounts of wastes and by-products from agriculture and agri-food processing industry.

Drying, juice production, jam production, frozen fruit and vegetables processing, pickles, cans, marmalade processings and spreads productions are common applications for fruit and vegetable industry. Solid and liquid residues containing a rich composition of dietary fibres, antioxidants, carbohydrates (fructose, glucose and saccharose), pectin, fatty acids and vitamins are generated during fruits and vegetables processings. For example, peels and seeds from the wastage are rich in phytochemicals allowing them to be used as flavoring agents and preservation compounds. Likewise, the vegetal tissues containing high amount of carotenoids, vitamins, and fibres are great sources to avoid human disease and disorders thanks to their capacity of antioxidants and antidiabetics (Ganesh, et al. 2022).

In citrus juice production, a half of the citrus is disposed as by-products. The production of pectin, limonen, flavour components, monosaccharids, and cellulose from the citrus wastes have been patented by Clark (2016). Besides these compounds, essential oils are also valuable components in citrus by-products used as flavoring ingredients for beverages, ice cream and other food products as well as being utilized in pharmaceuticals due to their effect of anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties (Boukroufa, et al. 2015). There are several studies about pectin production from citrus peel, banana peel, mango peel, apple pomace, sugar beet, passion fruit peel, watermelon waste, and pomegranate rind (Wang, et al. 2007, Masmoudi, et al. 2008, Cho, et al. 2019). Grape pomace produced in wine industry is another source of polyphenols (phenolic acids, anthocyanins, and flavanols) and having potential to be utilised in fruit juice as a colourant (Allison and Simmons 2018). Grape seed consists of high antioxidant and vitamin E (tocopherols and tocotrienols) which have beneficial effects for human health (Barba, et al. 2016). Tomato by-products particularly tomato peels known with its high lycopene content (Choudhari and Ananthanarayan 2007).

Olive pomace is a by-product of olive oil industry. It consists of wastewater, seed and shell and contains up to 8% oil depending on the extraction methods. Olive pomace is rich in polyphenols, fatty acids, pigments, tocopherols, and phytosterols. Milutinović, et al. (2015) studied the phenolic composition of the olive pomace due to its antioxidant, neurosedative, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, and anticancer properties. Additionally, there are plenty of studies in the extraction of the phenolics from olive pomace using different methods. For instance, Cea Pavez, et al. (2019) were reported high phenolic components in the extract obtained using pressured water. Goldsmith, et al. (2018) on the other hand, were used ultrasound to extract phenolics from olive pomace.

By-products from other plant-based waste

There has been large quantities of waste from other plant-based products discarded at every point along the food chain and households. Coffee processing systems can accumulate valuable residues such as coffee cut-steams, coffee silverskin, spent coffee grounds, coffee pulp, and coffee husk which are higher with carbohydrates, proteins, pectins and bioactive compounds (Aristizábal-Marulanda, et al. 2017, Dadi, et al. 2018). Spent coffee ground is generated after brewing from coffee machines by homemade or manufactures. This by-product is rich in lipids (palmitic and linoleic acids) and vitamin E, thus can be used as liposoluble antioxidant vitamins. Immature and

defective beans are sorted out during coffee harvesting and roasting processing to keep the quality of the coffee. These waste is rich in free amino acids and phenols. Therefore, they might be considered as a potential for the extraction of chlorogenic acid and caffeine in food and pharmaceutical industry. Coffee silverskin is also a possibility of the use as an antioxidant with content of melanoidins. In addition, coffee husk forms the outmost part which covers coffee bean, mucilage and silverskin, consisting of lignocellulosic polymers (cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin) thereby it has high potential to be used in food industry such as diet beverages, diet bread and biscuits (Hoseini, et al. 2021). Martinez-Saez, et al. (2014) studied coffee silverskin as an alternative body weight control beverage. They produced a beverage containing caffeine and chlorogenic acid using coffee silverskin, and it showed a significant impact on antioxidant activity. On the other hand, coffee silverskin was used for biofuels production such as biobutanol (Niglio, et al. 2019) and ethanol (Mussatto, et al. 2012) since it contains considerable amounts of carbohydrates and lignin. Coffee pulp contains phenolic acids, flavan-3-ols, hydroxycinnamic acids, flavonols, and anthocyanidins. Likewise, there has been wide researches on the phenolic compounds of coffee pulp (Ramirez-Coronel, et al. 2004; Farah and Donangelo 2006). In another study the antioxidant activity of spent coffee grounds and coffee husks has been evaluated. Coffee husks showed greater activity compared to spent coffee grounds. In addition, in this study, caffeine and chlorogenic acid were obtained from coffee husk using supercritical extraction (Andrade, et al. 2012).

During cocoa production, cocoa pod husk, cocoa bean shells and cocoa mucilage are produced as by-products. There are different applications of cocoa pod husk for various purposes. Martínez, et al. (2012) studied cocoa co-products (cocoa pod husk, cocoa bean shell and cocoa mucilage) as a natural compound and found that these by-products were superior in antioxidant activity. Cocoa pod husk is also a great source of pectin, lignocellulosic biomass, antioxidant capacity, energy production, and activated carbon. Sarmiento-Vásquez, et al. (2021) extracted fermentable sugars from cocoa pod husk to produce propionic acid. In other study, cocoa pod husk was used to investigate its possibility as a pectin source and findings showed that it was as productive as sugar-beet pulp pectin (Yapo and Koffi 2013). Cocoa bean shells, another by-product from cocoa or chocolate processing, are composed of 10%-17% of the total cocoa bean. Cocoa bean shells are rich in dietary fibers together with higher content of bioactive compounds such as polyphenols (Rojo-Poveda, et al. 2020). Barbosa-Pereira, et al. (2018) used pulsed electric field to extract polyphenols and methoxyanthines from cocoa bean shells and coffee silverskin and concluded that bioactive compounds were 20% more than those used by conventional extraction method. Cocoa mucilage is the whitish part which covers the cocoa bean, is used for alcohol production, vinegar, juice, citric acid, and cocoa jelly production. It consists of 10–14% fermentable sugars such as sucrose, glucose, and fructose, nutrients, pectin, proteins, citric acid, fibers, cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin (Rojasa, et al. 2020, Mendoza-Meneses, et al. 2021). Delgado-Noboa, et al. (2021) reported that cocoa mucilage had a great potential for production of bioethanol using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* yeast.

Tea is the one of the most consumed and popular beverages around the World. Tea waste is a lignocellulosic biomass composed of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, polyphenols, proteins and tannins. This waste consists of as same amounts of bioactive compounds as regular tea. Pruned leaves and branches of tea are wastes produced by tea processing and can be used because of its high content of cellulose, holocellulose, lignin and bioactive compounds. Likewise, tea leftover after infusion are also great source of bioactive compounds (Debnath, et al. 2021) In a study, tea waste was used for bio-fuel production (Uzun, et al. 2010) and for biogas production (Yadav, et al. 2016) due to higher lignin content.

2.2 Animal-Based Wastes

Meat products

Meat and meat-products cover an important part within the food industry. Different by-products of meat processing such as blood, fatty tissues, protein, bones, skin, etc. arise mainly during the slaughter of animals. Among several animal originated waste, blood is the major by-product in slaughterhouses and also rich in proteins such as albumin and fibrinogen. The application of the blood proteins have been widely studied for their nutritional value and functional properties, but today the use of the blood from meat is still a challenge with their limitations when implementing as a protein source in the food products. Out of the protein characteristics, the meat by-products are also high in lipids, fibres, and carbohydrates which have the possibility of using for biogas production along with reducing greenhouse emissions (Mofijur, et al. 2021). Collagen is another important content in the blood. Vidal, et al. (2020) investigated that 18% of collagen recovered from small cattle slaughtered residues. The collagen obtained from lamb showed higher foaming property compared to the collagen in sheep blood whereas viscosity was higher in the sheep blood. Chicken by-products can also be a source of gelatin, functional proteins, etc. Santana, et al. (2020) used the feet of chickens to gain gelatin and contrast to commercial gelatin, found that the gelatin produced from the chicken waste was selected in terms of sensory aspects. They also revealed that films prepared using the gelatin from chicken residues were similar to those commercial ingredients such as cellophane and latex.

Seafood products

Fish, marine animals and mollusks result in considerable amounts of waste or by-products (around 25-30% of total weight) during processing, production and storage. These by-products contains high amounts of collagen, natural pigments, fatty acids, chitin, chitosan, proteins, peptides, and calcium, are mainly used for animal feed, collagen and oil production. Therefore, these high value-added compounds are recovered by different methods to be utilised in various sectors such as pharmaceutical industries, cosmetic industries, and food industries. Due to their richness in polyunsaturated fatty acids, their applications are immense. Some fish and shellfish by-products are rich in carotenoids. Marine by-products (bones and shells) are also great sources of calcium. Additionally, the residues of the marine products are the source for the extraction of some enzymes. Shrimp shell can be used as a natural colorant and is also rich in vitamin E (Helkar, et al. 2016). Shrimp shell contains chitin and protein as well. Chitin and chitosan derived from chitin or its derivatives have antimicrobial, antitumor, antioxidant, antimutagenic, and cholesterol-lowering properties due to their biodegradability, thus can be used in various applications such as food industry, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries (Racioppo, et al. 2021). On the other hand, shrimp residues rich in bioactive compounds such as astaxanthin, are basically used to feed animal in the aquaculture farms (El-Bialy and Abd El-Khalek 2020). High amounts of proteins in the seafood being extracted from bones, viscera, liver, kidney, eggs, and skin by enzymatic or biological hydrolysis are more valuable than plant-based proteins and are great source for food supplements (Racioppo, et al. 2021).

Dairy products

Dairy production system is the largest part of the food industry among others. Large amounts of by-products are created during milk, cheese, yoghurt, butter and other dairy productions. Basically, casein and whey proteins form milk proteins. Whey, known as the most popular substrate, generated by cheese production is rich in both proteins and lactose and is used directly or indirectly in various food operations. Thanks to antimicrobial properties of lactoferrin against gram-positive or gram-negative bacteria, yeasts, viruses, etc., is one of the whey proteins obtained from cheese residues considered as a valuable bioactive compound (Dinika, et al. 2020). Lactose is the main

carbohydrate in the milk, for example, utilised in the food applications and is also transformed chemically, enzymatically, or microbiologically into galacto-oligosaccharides, lactulose, lactitol, lactobionic acid, hydrolyzed lactose, and tagatose. Fresh milk is centrifuged to remove impurities before processing, after the process remarkably high nutritional value of lees emerges that can be used for different purposes. Skimmilk, buttermilk and ghee are also produced during the manufacture of dairy products. Skim milk, a by-product of whipped cream production, functions as a moisture retainer in the standardization process in milk production or in spray drying. It consists of high non-fat solids (lactose and protein) and nutritional components used in the formulation of food products, fat-filled production, the content of protein standardization (Oliveira, et al. 2019). Among others, casein is the major protein in milk and total 80% of casein present in bovine, buffalo, caprine, or ovine milk particularly used in food and beverages applications. There is a wide range of study for the extraction of bioactive compounds from dairy industry side-streams. For instance, Silva and Hiibel (2021) studied dairy by-products to extract phosphorus and nitrogen by hydrothermal carbonization and membrane distillation. A possibility of obtaining nutritional components from whey occurred during dairy production has been performed by ultrafiltration in several research studies (Atra, et al. 2005, Baldasso, et al. 2011, Ilchenco, et al. 2018).

3. BASIC PRINCIPLES OF MICROWAVE-ASSISTED SOLVENT EXTRACTION

The effect of microwave energy in microwave-assisted solvent extraction systems depends on the dielectric properties of solvent and matrix (absorption, dielectric constant and loss factor). Dielectric constant (ϵ'), also known as relative permeability, indicates a measure of the ability of a material to be polarized by an external electric field (as that of microwaves) storing energy within it. Dielectric loss factor (ϵ'') represents the ability of the material to dissipate the absorbed electromagnetic energy, converting it into heat. The efficiency of the material subjected to microwave to transform electromagnetic energy into heat energy at a fixed frequency and temperature is measured by the loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) and this value is the ratio of the dielectric loss (ϵ'') to the dielectric constant (ϵ') of the material (Samanlı, et al. 2017). Thus, the materials low in the dielectric factor do not heat due to their transparent form for microwave while the materials with high dielectric loss factor is easily heated by microwave energy. On the other hand, in electrically conductive materials (as that of metals), microwaves reflect back from the surface and thus do not heat. Briefly, the materials absorbing microwaves such as water, sugar and oil can be heated by microwave. Solvents with low dipole moment (non-polar hexane and tetrahydrofuran) do not heat under microwave radiation, while solvents with high dipole moment (acetone and water) will heat within seconds. Therefore, the use of combination of different solvents in microwave-assisted solvent extractions are very common in order to provide the selectivity in extraction and/or to change the microwave behaviour of the medium in the desired direction. For instance, ionic liquids to increase microwave absorption capacity of the medium or polar materials such as alcohols or SiC which is ineffective as chemical, and high with microwave absorption ability can be supplemented to the medium. Another important issue is the water content of the matrix, which has high dielectric constant and dipole moment, provides localized superheating, allowing the component to be extracted to pass into the solvent easily. The water content of the matrix in MASE has thus to be controlled to obtain accurate and repeatable results.

As a result of the absorption of microwaves in materials exposed to microwaves, the basis of heating is based on the conduction of ions and dipole rotation (rotation) mechanisms caused by this electric field (Kaufmann and Christen 2002). These two mechanisms occur simultaneously in most applications. Ionic conduction is the electrophoretic migration of ions when a magnetic field is applied. Dissolved charged particles participating in the oscillatory motion under the influence of a variable electric field collide with adjacent molecules, thereby heat the solution (Gjuraj, et al. 2012).

Dipole rotation means reconstructing of dipoles with microwave radiation occurring mostly in a frequency of 2.45 GHz. As a result of friction force generated by molecular rotation, a quick heating develops (Kaufmann and Christen 2002). Thus, the whole system in MASE including solvent and sample heat simultaneously compared with traditional heating concepts. Hence

Finally MASE can be described as a technique in which microwave radiation is used to heat the medium to help the transfer of the solutes from the matrix into the solvent. In some cases, microwave energy applications provide non-thermal effect to the extraction. Localized heating causes the cell walls to widen and rupture in the samples, thus allowing extractable components to pass easily into the solvent (Haswell and Kingston 1997).

3.1. Microwave Extraction Systems

Closed (under pressure) vessel and open (under atmospheric pressure) vessel operations can be applied in microwave systems. Closed-vessel in MASE which can be controlled under pressure and temperature is the most favored system. As the pressure increases in the closed-vessel systems, the solvents used can be heated to higher temperatures than the boiling point at atmospheric pressure. The pressure of the vessel in the closed-vessel design changes depending on the boiling point and of volume of the solvent applied. Another disadvantage of the closed-vessel designs is to cool down the system until room temperature before opening the vessel. The maximum power in the closed-vessel systems is between 600 and 1000 W (Destandau, 2013).

The process is conducted under atmospheric pressure in the open vessel system, so temperature of the solvent is limited by its boiling point at atmospheric pressure. The solvent heated and evaporated is condensed through the reflux and again sent back to the vessel. Meanwhile, MW placed on the vessel generate fast and homogeneous heating. Despite the safety of the open vessel system, the extraction of large quantities of samples at once can be processed in the open vessel design compared with the closed-vessel designs.

There are also various modified microwave extraction systems used in scientific researches. For example, vacuum microwave-assisted extraction systems which moderate working conditions are provided, has been developed for the extraction of sensitive components. The mass transfer mechanism of active compounds from substance to solvent is resulted by suction pressure in these systems. Nitrogen-protected microwave-assisted extraction is another type of modified microwave extraction system where nitrogen is used to keep the extraction vessel under pressure and to prevent oxidation of oxygen sensitive molecules during extraction. The combined systems in which microwave and ultrasonic waves are used to intensify mass transfer mechanism, has been also developed. Dynamic microwave-assisted extraction systems where the extraction process is applied continuously and automatically as well as combined with a non-linear analytical step is another example (Llompart, 2019).

Microwave designs have been developed as lab-scaled therefore only milligrams of product could be obtained over the years. However, today, versatile microwave-powered continuous flow reactors that can easily be integrated into a wide variety of processes and capacities up to tens of thousands of liters per hour have been designed and manufactured commercially to eliminate this advantage.

Microwave heating is faster, more efficient, cleaner, greener and safer than traditional heating methods. Particularly the systems designed for extraction have advantages such as increasing the concentration of the components, decreasing the solvent requirement and short time, yet it has also disadvantages such as high investment cost and the necessity of a filtration process to separate the solid phase after extraction.

3.2 The Effect of Microwave Parameters on Extraction Efficiency

Solvent's nature and volume, extraction temperature, extraction time and microwave power are such important parameters for enhancing extraction productivity in MASE technique. In many studies, MASE parameters have been optimized using different factors to have the highest efficiency in MASE. The effects and interaction between these parameters are important to understand the MASE process. Therefore, this part will highlight the importance of accurate selection for the operation parameters with an optimum productivity.

Solvent and solvent volume

An adequate choice of solvent is a critical factor for obtaining optimal extraction yield in MASE and can influence the efficiency of the extraction process. If the solvent with high values of dielectric constant is used in the process, the solvent capacity will be higher for absorption of microwave energy. The dielectric constant shows the capability of the solvent to be polarized by an external electric field storing energy within it (Gala, et al. 2018). The solvent interaction with the matrix, solvent properties, and the analyte solubility in the solvent should be taken into account when implementing the process. In order to remove undesirable components, for example in the extraction of pesticides and organic pollutants from soil, high selectivity towards analyte is very important for the solvent's choice.

Although MASE requires less solvent, less extraction time, high productivity etc. than conventional systems, the optimum extraction is not always favor of those used in MASE. For instance, the yield extracted using MASE with hexane as a solvent was lower than used with soxhlet extraction because its transparency function prevents to be heated by microwave. However, the extraction yield was higher when ethanol used in MASE than soxhlet method due to better ability of absorption capacity of microwave. Therefore, dielectric properties of the solvent play an important role for an optimal production (Mandal, et al. 2007). In this case, due to lower dielectric constant and dissipation factor of non-polar solvents, microwave does not heat the non-polar solvents. Among polar solvents water with its high dielectric constant has an excellent efficiency in microwave absorption. Despite ethanol and methanol are both polar but lower than water again associated with dielectric constant, they perform higher efficiency when mixed with water (Rafiee, et al. 2011). Further, Rodriguez-Padron, et al. (2020) investigated the extraction of phenolic compounds from green walnut shell residues by MASE with different solvents (water, water:ethanol, water:acetonitrile, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate, and acetonitrile) and the combination of water:acetonitrile was superior for this extraction method. Therefore, different solvents can be integrated for microwave process and this in turn can improve the productivity of the extraction. The extraction productivity relies on the analytes' solubility in the extraction solvent that can be either polar or non-polar in MASE. Particularly flavonoids can act differently in polarity, thus can be polar or less polar. Less polar solvents (benzene, chloroform, ether, and ethyl acetate) generally are used to extract flavonoid aglycones (isoflavones, flavanones, flavones, etc.) whereas more polar solvents (water, ethanol, methanol, and acetone) are implied for extracting of flavonoid glycosides (flavonols, hydroxylated flavones, auronol, etc.) and anthocyanin (Routray and Orsat 2012).

Solvent volume is another parameter affecting extraction productivity in MASE. During irradiation time, plant components used in MASE must be entirely immersed in the solvent, the volume of the solvent is therefore crucial with respect to the amount of sample (Mandal, et al. 2007). According to research by Maran, Sivakumar et al. (2013) after microwave extraction of pectin from orange peel, pectin yield increased when increasing the solid:liquid ratio up to 1:16 g/mL due to swelling of the materials with higher volume of liquids and absorbing microwave irradiation by the material, thus resulting in the cleavage of the cell walls. However, increasing the extraction solvent does not always provide high extraction efficiency. If the solvent volume is too high, it will not be able to

provide enough energy to heat the solvent, resulting in reduced extraction efficiency (Nguyen, et al. 2020).

Microwave power and temperature

In MASE, the extraction temperature is proportional to the applied microwave power, increasing power leads to rapid internal heat generation (Pereira, et al. 2007). In general, high temperature lowers the surface tension and viscosity of the solvent, thereby increasing the wetting and penetration effect of solvent, and ultimately facilitating the transfer of the analyte from matrix to the solvent in extraction process (Eskilsson and Björklund 2000). On the other hand, low microwave power slows down the molecular movement and prolongs the extraction time (Mwaurah, et al. 2020). Hence it is important to determine the optimum power requirement in the microwave assisted extraction process. Some studies reported that the extraction yield enhanced with increasing temperature but a decrease revealed after an optimum temperature. Some publications have shown that prolonged processing at elevated temperature or elevated temperature causes degradation of heat sensitive compounds, reducing the yield and/or purity of target compounds. For instance, Alara and Abdurahman (2019) reported that the extraction efficiency increased when the microwave power was increased up to a certain power, and the efficiency began to decrease with further power application, in the study where phenolic compounds was extracted from Hibiscus with MASE. Likewise, Kurtulbaş Şahin, et al. (2021) was reported that phenolic recovery reduced after an optimum microwave power in the study where phenolic compounds and anthocyanins extracted from sour cherry peels by MASE. Zhang, et al. (2022) reported that high microwave power cause destruction of cell and accelerates the oil extraction yield from *C. oleifera* seed. However it was also reported that the structure of *C. oleifera* oil was damaged by too high microwave energy application.

Extraction time

Extraction time is a key variable that influence the efficiency of the extraction. Generally, increasing the extraction time causes to increase in yield. On the other hand extending the time excessively can reduce the yield due to some undesirable reactions, such as enzymatic degradation, oxidation, etc. Therefore extraction time is another critical parameter should be optimized for a MASE process. Dhobi, Mandal et al. (2009) examined the extraction of silybinin by microwave assisted extraction and reported that the yield of silybinin increased over time, but there was no change in yield after 6 minutes. Xiaokang, et al. (2020) reported that total phenolic content and antioxidant activity decreased with an over extension of extraction time in MASE of polyphenols from shiitake mushrooms. Similarly, Kaderides, et al. (2019) reported that longer extraction times after 4 minutes reduced the extraction yield of phenolics from pomegranate peel.

3.3 Applications of Microwave-Assisted Solvent Extraction From Food Waste

Microwave heating is an alternative and advantageous heating method compared to conventional heating. Many processes that require heating, such as drying, extraction, and synthesis, can be performed efficiently using microwave heating. The systems used microwave energy provide short reaction time and higher reaction yield than traditional heating systems. Therefore, microwave heating has been considered as an alternative method to recover valuable components from food waste. There has been an increase in studies on this subject in recent years. The microwave-assisted extraction system, the recovered components, extraction conditions and the solvents used in extraction in the literature are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Literature summary for the application of microwave assisted extraction

Target component	By-product	Microwave system	Extraction conditions (Solvent, sample quantity, power, temperature, time)	References
Pectin	Apple pomace	Open vessel	HCl solution; 2 g; 499,4 W; 20.8 min	(Wang, et al. 2007)
Pectin	Grapefruit peel	Open vessel	Water (pH 1.5); 6 g; 900 W; 6 min	(Bagherian, et al. 2011)
Pectin	Mango peel	Open vessel	Water; 413 W; 134 s	(Maran, et al. 2015)
Pectin	Papaya peel	Household microwave oven	Water; 512 W; 140 s	(Maran and Prakash 2015)
Pectin	Sour orange peel	Microwave oven	Citric acid solution; 700 W; 3 min	(Hosseini, et al. 2016)
Pectin	Sugar beet pulp	Microwave oven	Sulfuric acid solution; ~152 W; 3.53 min	(Li, et al. 2012)
Phenolic acids	Mandarin peels	Open vessel	Methanol (66%); 5 g; 152 W; 49 s	(Hayat, et al. 2009)
Phenolic compounds	Peanut skin	Closed vessel	Ethanol (30%); 1.5 g; 855 W; 150 s	(Ballard, et al. 2010)
Phenolic acid	Mandarin peel	Closed vessel	Water; 1 g; 400 W; 135 °C; 3 min	(Ahmad and Langrish 2012)
Phenolic compounds	Potato processing wastes	Closed vessel	Ethanol (60%); 0.5 g; 300 W; 80 °C; 2 min	(Wu, et al. 2012)
Phenolic compounds	Olive pomace	Closed vessel	Choline chlorite: citric acid (1:2); 2 g; 200 W; 30 min	(Chanioti and Tzia 2018)
Phenolic compounds	Olive pomace	Closed vessel	Ethanol (20%); 700 W; 10 min	(Jurmanović, et al. 2019)
Phenolic compounds	Pistachio hull	Closed vessel	Ethanol (56%); 1 g; 140 W, 4.5 min	(Özbek, et al. 2020)
Phenolic compounds	Wine lees	Closed vessel	Ethanol (75%); HCl (1%); 2 g; 200 W; 17 min	(Pérez-Serradilla and De Castro 2011)
Phenolic compounds	Red grape pomace	Closed vessel	Water or water:ethanol (1:1); 2 g; 200 W; 50 °C; 60 min	(Drosou, et al. 2015)
Polyphenols and flavanoids	<i>Achillea millefolium</i> (yarrov) dust	Household microwave oven	Ethanol–water; 3 g; 170 W; 33 s	(Milutinović, et al. 2015)

Target component	By-product	Microwave system	Extraction conditions (Solvent, sample quantity, power, temperature, time)	References
Essential oil	Grapefruit peel	Open vessel	Solvent-free; 250 g; 85 W; 20 min	(Uysal, et al. 2011)
Oil	Olive pomace	Closed vessel	Hexane; 2.5 g; 287 W; 16 min	(Yanık 2017)
Maslinic and oleanolic acids	Olive pomace	Closed vessel	Hexane; 2 g; 150-300 W; 4-20 min	(Biltekin, et al. 2022)
Maslinic and oleanolic acids	Olive pomace	Open vessel	Ethanol: water (9:1 v/v); 40 °C (10 min for MA, 2.93 min for OA)	(Ozkan, et al. 2017)
2-furfural and 5-HMF	Wheat straw	Closed vessel	H ₂ O/HCl; 140-190 °C; 1-30 min	(Yemiş and Mazza 2012)
Bioactive carbohydrates (inositol and inulin)	Artichoke external bracts	Closed vessel	Water; 0.1 g; 900 W; 50 °C; 3 min	(Ruiz-Aceituno, et al. 2016)
Fermentable sugars	Cotton plant residue	Household microwave oven	Alkaline water; 300 W, 6 min	(Vani, et al. 2012)
Ferulic acid	Brewery by-product	Closed vessel	H ₂ O/ NaOH (0.5%); 1 g; 100 °C; 15 min	(Moreira, et al. 2012)
Gelatine	Duck feet	Household microwave oven	350 W, 5 min	(Chanioti and Tzia 2018)
D-limonene	Orange peel	Closed vessel	Hexane; 1 g; 200 W; 110 °C; 30 min	(Attard, et al. 2014)
Carotenoids	Carrot juice processing waste	Closed vessel	Flaxseed oil; 8.06 g; 165 W; 9.39 min	(Elik, et al. 2020)
Lycopene	Tomato peel	Closed vessel	Ethyl acetate; 1-2-4 g; 400 W; 1 min	(Ho, et al. 2015)
Non-polar compounds	Pistachio hull	Closed vessel	Hexane; 1.5 g; 250 W; 12.5 min	(Özbek, et al. 2018)

Microwave assisted extraction has been frequently used in the extraction of phenolic compounds from various food wastes. It has been reported that the components are obtained in a very short time and/or with higher extraction efficiency compared to conventional methods with microwave assisted extraction. In conventional extraction systems (eg soxhlet extraction), process is completed between 3-6 hours, while this time is limited to minutes in microwave heating. Li, et al. (2011) emphasized that more than 90% of the polyphenols of grape seed are extracted with the microwave system in just a few minutes. Liazid, et al. (2011) extracted anthocyanins with a notable short extraction time (5 min) from grape skins by microwave assisted extraction. Mirzapour-Kouhdasht, et al. (2019) and Binsi, et al. (2017) successfully extracted the colloidal gelatin from by-products of fish using microwave assisted extraction. Also, Park, et al. (2013) reported that gelatin obtained by MASE from duck feet had better quality properties than those obtained by other methods. Yanık

(2017) obtained higher quality oil in a very short time (16 min) from olive pomace using MASE compared to soxhlet extraction. Keskin Çavdar, et al. (2017) reported that pomegranate seed oil extracted by MASE had significantly lower peroxide value, free fatty acidity and higher total phenolic content and antioxidant activity than those of the oil obtained by cold extraction. Traditionally, pectin was extracted in acidic solution at about 90°C for at least 1 hour, while Hosseini, et al. (2016) successfully extracted pectin with an appropriate purity from sour orange peel within 3 minutes by MASE. Wang, et al. (2007) extracted pectin from apple pulp within 20 minutes. Ho, et al. (2015) conducted studies on obtaining lycopene from tomato peel by microwave heating and showed that while conventional extraction showed a high yield of cis-lycopene, MASE significantly improved trans and total lycopene yield. Binod, et al. (2012) demonstrated that short-term microwave pretreatment significantly improves yield in obtaining fermentable sugar from sugar cane pulp. Vani, et al. (2012) compared the hydrolysis performance of microwave-assisted alkaline pretreatment and high pressure pretreatment to obtain fermentable sugars from cotton plant wastes. They reported that bioethanol can be produced with 5 times lower energy requirement in microwave application compared to high pressure application. Some studies have been carried out on the separation of lignocellulosic components by using different sources with microwave application, and the production of sugars that can be used for different. In these studies, while an increase in yield was obtained, it was observed that toxic by-products were also reduced (Zhu, et al. 2015; Singh, et al. 2017). Jurmanović, et al. (2019) successfully extract the phenolic compounds from olive pomace using ethanol by MASE in a few minutes. Similarly, Chanioti and Tzia (2018) emphasized that the MASE was an effective technique for the extraction of phenolic compounds from olive pomace.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Valorization of food industry by-products is essential to reduce its threatens effects on environment, economy and food insecurity. The studies on the utilization of the food by products are increasing gradually and valorization of food waste and losses will continue to be a hot topic in the coming years. Microwave-assisted extraction can replace conventional methods for the recovery of target components such as polyphenols, oil, essential oil, pectin, fermentable sugars, etc. from food waste. Studies cited in this review figure out that microwave-assisted extraction method shortens the processing time, reduces the solvent consumption, increases the extraction yield and minimizes the deterioration of these target components. Most of the work in the literature on microwave extraction is lab-scale and batch operation, there are limited number of studies on pilot scale and/or continuous microwave extraction systems. Future studies should concentrated on pilot scale studies on the extraction of valuable components with MASE and should reveal also the efficiency and quality impact of this technique as well as its energy consumption and economic advantages.

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REFERENCES

- Agu, O. S., L. G. Tabil & T. Dumonceaux (2017). "Microwave-assisted alkali pre-treatment, densification and enzymatic saccharification of canola straw and oat hull." *Bioengineering* **4**(2): 25.
- Ahmad, J. & T. Langrish (2012). "Optimisation of total phenolic acids extraction from mandarin peels using microwave energy: The importance of the Maillard reaction." *Journal of Food Engineering* **109**(1): 162-174.
- Akyol, H., Y. Riciputi, E. Capanoglu, M. F. Caboni & V. Verardo (2016). "Phenolic compounds in the potato and its byproducts: an overview." *International journal of molecular sciences* **17**(6): 835.
- Alara, O. R. and N. H. Abdurahman (2019). "Microwave-assisted extraction of phenolics from Hibiscus sabdariffa calyces: Kinetic modelling and process intensification." *Industrial Crops and Products* **137**: 528-535.
- Allison, B. J. & C. W. Simmons (2018). "Obtaining multiple coproducts from red grape pomace via anthocyanin extraction and biogas production." *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry* **66**(30): 8045-8053.
- Andrade, K. S., R. T. Gonçalves, M. Maraschin, R. M. Ribeiro-do-Valle, J. Martínez & S. R. Ferreira (2012). "Supercritical fluid extraction from spent coffee grounds and coffee husks: Antioxidant activity and effect of operational variables on extract composition." *Talanta* **88**: 544-552.
- Aristizábal-Marulanda, V., Y. Chacón-Perez & C. A. C. Alzate (2017). The biorefinery concept for the industrial valorization of coffee processing by-products. *Handbook of Coffee Processing By-Products*, Elsevier: 63-92.
- Atra, R., G. Vatai, E. Bekassy-Molnar & A. Balint (2005). "Investigation of ultra-and nanofiltration for utilization of whey protein and lactose." *Journal of food engineering* **67**(3): 325-332.
- Attard, T. M., B. Watterson, V. L. Budarin, J. H. Clark & A. J. Hunt (2014). "Microwave assisted extraction as an important technology for valorising orange waste." *New Journal of Chemistry* **38**(6): 2278-2283.
- Azmir, J., I. S. M. Zaidul, M. M. Rahman, K. Sharif, A. Mohamed, F. Sahena, M. Jahurul, K. Ghafoor, N. Norulaini & A. Omar (2013). "Techniques for extraction of bioactive compounds from plant materials: A review." *Journal of food engineering* **117**(4): 426-436.
- Bagherian, H., F. Z. Ashtiani, A. Fouladitajar & M. Mohtashamy (2011). "Comparisons between conventional, microwave-and ultrasound-assisted methods for extraction of pectin from grapefruit." *Chemical engineering and processing: Process Intensification* **50**(11-12): 1237-1243.
- Baldasso, C., T. Barros & I. Tessaro (2011). "Concentration and purification of whey proteins by ultrafiltration." *Desalination* **278**(1-3): 381-386.
- Ballard, T. S., P. Mallikarjunan, K. Zhou & S. O'Keefe (2010). "Microwave-assisted extraction of phenolic antioxidant compounds from peanut skins." *Food chemistry* **120**(4): 1185-1192.
- Barba, F. J., Z. Zhu, M. Koubaa, A. S. Sant'Ana & V. Orlien (2016). "Green alternative methods for the extraction of antioxidant bioactive compounds from winery wastes and by-products: A review." *Trends in Food Science & Technology* **49**: 96-109.

- Barbosa-Pereira, L., A. Guglielmetti & G. Zeppa (2018). "Pulsed electric field assisted extraction of bioactive compounds from cocoa bean shell and coffee silverskin." *Food and bioprocess technology* **11**(4): 818-835.
- Biltekin, S. İ., F. Göğüş & D. K. Yanık (2022). "Valorization of Olive Pomace: Extraction of Maslinic and Oleanolic by Using Closed Vessel Microwave Extraction System." *Waste and Biomass Valorization* **13**(3): 1599-1608.
- Binod, P., K. Satyanagalakshmi, R. Sindhu, K. U. Janu, R. K. Sukumaran & A. Pandey (2012). "Short duration microwave assisted pretreatment enhances the enzymatic saccharification and fermentable sugar yield from sugarcane bagasse." *Renewable Energy* **37**(1): 109-116.
- Binsi, P., N. Nayak, P. Sarkar, C. Joshy, G. Ninan & C. Ravishankar (2017). "Gelation and thermal characteristics of microwave extracted fish gelatin–natural gum composite gels." *Journal of food science and technology* **54**(2): 518-530.
- Boukid, F. (2021). "Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) protein as a prospective plant-based ingredient: a review." *International Journal of Food Science & Technology* **56**(11): 5435-5444.
- Boukroufa, M., C. Boutekedjiret, L. Petigny, N. Rakotomanomana & F. Chemat (2015). "Bio-refinery of orange peels waste: A new concept based on integrated green and solvent free extraction processes using ultrasound and microwave techniques to obtain essential oil, polyphenols and pectin." *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry* **24**: 72-79.
- Cea Pavez, I., J. Lozano-Sánchez, I. Borrás-Linares, H. Nuñez, P. Robert & A. Segura-Carretero (2019). "Obtaining an extract rich in phenolic compounds from olive pomace by pressurized liquid extraction." *Molecules* **24**(17): 3108.
- Chanioti, S. & C. Tzia (2018). "Extraction of phenolic compounds from olive pomace by using natural deep eutectic solvents and innovative extraction techniques." *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies* **48**: 228-239.
- Cho, E.-H., H.-T. Jung, B.-H. Lee, H.-S. Kim, J.-K. Rhee & S.-H. Yoo (2019). "Green process development for apple-peel pectin production by organic acid extraction." *Carbohydrate polymers* **204**: 97-103.
- Choudhari, S. M. & L. Ananthanarayan (2007). "Enzyme aided extraction of lycopene from tomato tissues." *Food chemistry* **102**(1): 77-81.
- Clark, J. H., Pfaltzgraff, L.A., Budarin, V. L., & De Bruyn, M. (2016). Microwave Assisted Citrus Waste Borefinery. United States Patent. US 9,382,339 B2.
- Dadi, D., A. Beyene, K. Simoens, J. Soares, M. Demeke, J. Thevelein, K. Bernaerts, P. Luis & B. Van der Bruggen (2018). "Valorization of coffee byproducts for bioethanol production using lignocellulosic yeast fermentation and pervaporation." *International journal of environmental science and technology* **15**(4): 821-832.
- Debnath, B., D. Haldar & M. K. Purkait (2021). "Potential and sustainable utilization of tea waste: A review on present status and future trends." *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* **9**(5): 106179.
- Delgado-Noboa, J., T. Bernal, J. Soler & J. Á. Pena (2021). "Kinetic modeling of batch bioethanol production from CCN-51 Cocoa Mucilage." *Journal of the Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers* **128**: 169-175.
- Destandau, E., Michel, T., & Elfakir, C. ((2013).). *Microwave-assisted Extraction. Natural Product Extraction: Principles and Applications* m. A. R. v. J. M. Prado. Cambridge, UK, RSC Publishing: 113-156.

- Dhobi, M., V. Mandal & S. Hemalatha (2009). "Optimization of microwave assisted extraction of bioactive flavonolignan-silybinin." *Journal of chemical metrology* **3**(1): 13.
- Dinika, I., D. K. Verma, R. Balia, G. L. Utama & A. R. Patel (2020). "Potential of cheese whey bioactive proteins and peptides in the development of antimicrobial edible film composite: A review of recent trends." *Trends in Food Science & Technology* **103**: 57-67.
- Drosou, C., K. Kyriakopoulou, A. Bimpilas, D. Tsimogiannis & M. Krokida (2015). "A comparative study on different extraction techniques to recover red grape pomace polyphenols from vinification byproducts." *Industrial Crops and Products* **75**: 141-149.
- El-Bialy, H. A. A. & H. H. Abd El-Khalek (2020). "A comparative study on astaxanthin recovery from shrimp wastes using lactic fermentation and green solvents: an applied model on minced Tilapia." *Journal of Radiation Research and Applied Sciences* **13**(1): 594-605.
- Elik, A., D. K. Yanık & F. Göğüş (2020). "Microwave-assisted extraction of carotenoids from carrot juice processing waste using flaxseed oil as a solvent." *Lwt* **123**: 109100.
- Eskilsson, C. S. & E. Björklund (2000). "Analytical-scale microwave-assisted extraction." *Journal of chromatography A* **902**(1): 227-250.
- FAO (2021). *Fruit & Vegetables – Your Dietary Essentials*. Retrieved from: <https://www.fao.org/3/cb2395en/cb2395en.pdf> Accessed 11 Feb 2022.
- FAO (2011). *Global food losses and food waste-Extent, causes and prevention*. Rome. Retrieved from: <https://www.fao.org/3/i2697e/i2697e.pdf> 8 Feb 2022.
- Farah, A. & C. M. Donangelo (2006). "Phenolic compounds in coffee." *Brazilian journal of plant physiology* **18**: 23-36.
- Gala, S., S. Sumarno & M. Mahfud (2018). *Microwave-assisted extraction of natural dyes from Coleus atropurpureus leaves: The effect of solvent*. MATEC Web of Conferences, EDP Sciences.
- Ganesh, K. S., A. Sridhar & S. Vishali (2022). "Utilization of fruit and vegetable waste to produce value-added products: Conventional utilization and emerging opportunities-A review." *Chemosphere* **287**: 132221.
- Gao, Y., X. Guo, Y. Liu, Z. Fang, M. Zhang, R. Zhang, L. You, T. Li & R. H. Liu (2018). "A full utilization of rice husk to evaluate phytochemical bioactivities and prepare cellulose nanocrystals." *Scientific reports* **8**(1): 1-8.
- Gjuraj, E., R. Kongoli & G. Shore (2012). "Combination of flow reactors with microwave-assisted synthesis: smart engineering concept for steering synthetic chemistry on the "fast lane"." *Chemical and Biochemical Engineering Quarterly* **26**(3): 285-307.
- Goldsmith, C. D., Q. V. Vuong, C. E. Stathopoulos, P. D. Roach & C. J. Scarlett (2018). "Ultrasound increases the aqueous extraction of phenolic compounds with high antioxidant activity from olive pomace." *LWT* **89**: 284-290.
- Haswell, S. J. & H. M. Kingston (1997). *Microwave-enhanced chemistry: fundamentals, sample preparation, and applications*, American Chemical Society.
- Hayat, K., S. Hussain, S. Abbas, U. Farooq, B. Ding, S. Xia, C. Jia, X. Zhang & W. Xia (2009). "Optimized microwave-assisted extraction of phenolic acids from citrus mandarin peels and evaluation of antioxidant activity in vitro." *Separation and Purification Technology* **70**(1): 63-70.
- Helkar, P. B., A. K. Sahoo & N. Patil (2016). "Review: Food industry by-products used as a functional food ingredients." *International Journal of Waste Resources* **6**(3): 1-6.

- Ho, K. K., M. Ferruzzi, A. Liceaga & M. F. San Martín-González (2015). "Microwave-assisted extraction of lycopene in tomato peels: Effect of extraction conditions on all-trans and cis-isomer yields." *LWT-Food Science and Technology* **62**(1): 160-168.
- Hoseini, M., S. Cocco, C. Casucci, V. Cardelli & G. Corti (2021). "Coffee by-products derived resources. A review." *Biomass and Bioenergy* **148**: 106009.
- Hosseini, S. S., F. Khodaiyan & M. S. Yarmand (2016). "Optimization of microwave assisted extraction of pectin from sour orange peel and its physicochemical properties." *Carbohydrate polymers* **140**: 59-65.
- Ikram-Ul-Haq, H. U., Z. Mahmood & M. M. Javed (2012). "Solid state fermentation for the production of α -amylase by *Paenibacillus amylolyticus*." *Pak J Bot* **44**: 341-346.
- Iltchenco, S., D. Preci, C. Bonifacino, E. F. Fraguas, C. Steffens, L. A. Panizzolo, R. Colet, I. A. Fernandes, C. Abirached & E. Valduga (2018). "Whey protein concentration by ultrafiltration and study of functional properties." *Ciência Rural* **48**.
- Jurmanović, S., M. Jug, T. Safner, K. Radić, A. DOMIJAN, S. Pedisić, S. Šimić, J. Jablan & D. V. Čepo (2019). "Utilization of olive pomace as a source of polyphenols: Optimization of microwave-assisted extraction and characterization of spray-dried extract." *Journal of Food & Nutrition Research* **58**(1).
- Kaderides, K., L. Papaoikonomou, M. Serafim & A. M. Goula (2019). "Microwave-assisted extraction of phenolics from pomegranate peels: Optimization, kinetics, and comparison with ultrasounds extraction." *Chemical Engineering and Processing-Process Intensification* **137**: 1-11.
- Kaufmann, B. & P. Christen (2002). "Recent extraction techniques for natural products: microwave-assisted extraction and pressurised solvent extraction." *Phytochemical Analysis: An International Journal of Plant Chemical and Biochemical Techniques* **13**(2): 105-113.
- Keskin Çavdar, H., D. Koçak Yanık, U. Gök & F. Göğüş (2017). "Optimisation of microwave-assisted extraction of pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.) seed oil and evaluation of its physicochemical and bioactive properties." *Food technology and biotechnology* **55**(1): 86-94.
- Kılıç, G. (1999). Evaluation of Durum Clear Flour, A MSc Thesis in Food Engineering Department, University of Gaziantep.
- Kim, T.-K., Y.-K. Ham, D.-M. Shin, H.-W. Kim, H. W. Jang, Y.-B. Kim & Y.-S. Choi (2020). "Extraction of crude gelatin from duck skin: effects of heating methods on gelatin yield." *Poultry science* **99**(1): 590-596.
- Kurtulbaş Şahin, E., M. Bilgin & S. Şahin (2021). "Recovery of anthocyanins from sour cherry (*Prunus cerasus* L.) peels via microwave assisted extraction: Monitoring the storage stability." *Preparative Biochemistry & Biotechnology* **51**(7): 686-696.
- Li, D.-q., X. Jia, Z. Wei & Z.-y. Liu (2012). "Box–Behnken experimental design for investigation of microwave-assisted extracted sugar beet pulp pectin." *Carbohydrate Polymers* **88**(1): 342-346.
- Li, Y., G. K. Skouroumounis, G. M. Elsey & D. K. Taylor (2011). "Microwave-assistance provides very rapid and efficient extraction of grape seed polyphenols." *Food Chemistry* **129**(2): 570-576.
- Liaqid, A., R. Guerrero, E. Cantos, M. Palma & C. Barroso (2011). "Microwave assisted extraction of anthocyanins from grape skins." *Food chemistry* **124**(3): 1238-1243.
- Llompарт, M., Garcia-Jares, C., Celeiro, M., & Dagnac, T. (2019). Microwave-Assisted extraction. *Encyclopedia of Analytical Science*. A. T. P. Worsfold, C. Poole ve M. Miró Amsterdam, Netherlands, Elsevier.: 67-77.

- Lu, X., Z. Zheng, H. Li, R. Cao, Y. Zheng, H. Yu, J. Xiao, S. Miao & B. Zheng (2017). "Optimization of ultrasonic-microwave assisted extraction of oligosaccharides from lotus (*Nelumbo nucifera* Gaertn.) seeds." *Industrial Crops and Products* **107**: 546-557.
- Mandal, V., Y. Mohan & S. Hemalatha (2007). "Microwave assisted extraction—an innovative and promising extraction tool for medicinal plant research." *Pharmacognosy reviews* **1**(1): 7-18.
- Maran, J. P. & K. A. Prakash (2015). "Process variables influence on microwave assisted extraction of pectin from waste *Carcia papaya* L. peel." *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* **73**: 202-206.
- Maran, J. P., V. Sivakumar, K. Thirugnanasambandham & R. Sridhar (2013). "Optimization of microwave assisted extraction of pectin from orange peel." *Carbohydrate polymers* **97**(2): 703-709.
- Maran, J. P., K. Swathi, P. Jeevitha, J. Jayalakshmi & G. Ashvini (2015). "Microwave-assisted extraction of pectic polysaccharide from waste mango peel." *Carbohydrate polymers* **123**: 67-71.
- Martinez-Saez, N., M. Ullate, M. A. Martin-Cabrejas, P. Martorell, S. Genovés, D. Ramon & M. D. del Castillo (2014). "A novel antioxidant beverage for body weight control based on coffee silverskin." *Food chemistry* **150**: 227-234.
- Martínez, R., P. Torres, M. Meneses, J. Figueroa, J. Pérez-Álvarez & M. Viuda-Martos (2012). "Chemical, technological and in vitro antioxidant properties of cocoa (*Theobroma cacao* L.) co-products." *Food Research International* **49**(1): 39-45.
- Masmoudi, M., S. Besbes, M. Chaabouni, C. Robert, M. Paquot, C. Blecker & H. Attia (2008). "Optimization of pectin extraction from lemon by-product with acidified date juice using response surface methodology." *Carbohydrate polymers* **74**(2): 185-192.
- Mendoza-Meneses, C., A. Feregrino-Pérez & C. Gutiérrez-Antonio (2021). "Potential Use of Industrial Cocoa Waste in Biofuel Production." *Journal of Chemistry* **2021**.
- Milutinović, M., N. Radovanović, M. Ćorović, S. Šiler-Marinković, M. Rajilić-Stojanović & S. Dimitrijević-Branković (2015). "Optimisation of microwave-assisted extraction parameters for antioxidants from waste *Achillea millefolium* dust." *Industrial Crops and Products* **77**: 333-341.
- Mirzapour-Kouhdasht, A., F. Sabzipour, M. S. Taghizadeh & M. Moosavi-Nasab (2019). "Physicochemical, rheological, and molecular characterization of colloidal gelatin produced from Common carp by-products using microwave and ultrasound-assisted extraction." *Journal of texture studies* **50**(5): 416-425.
- Mofijur, M., I. R. Fattah, P. S. Kumar, S. Y. A. Siddiki, S. A. Rahman, S. Ahmed, H. C. Ong, S. S. Lam, I. A. Badruddin & T. Y. Khan (2021). "Bioenergy recovery potential through the treatment of the meat processing industry waste in Australia." *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* **9**(4): 105657.
- Mona, E. M. & M. E. A. Amani (2008). "Production of \hat{I}^2 -mannanase by *Bacillus amylolequifaciens* 10A1 cultured on potato peels." *African Journal of Biotechnology* **7**(8): 1123-1128.
- Moreira, M. M., S. Morais, A. A. Barros, C. Delerue-Matos & L. F. Guido (2012). "A novel application of microwave-assisted extraction of polyphenols from brewer's spent grain with HPLC-DAD-MS analysis." *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry* **403**(4): 1019-1029.
- Mullen, A. M., C. Álvarez, M. Pojić, T. D. Hadnadev & M. Papageorgiou (2015). *Classification and target compounds. Food waste recovery*, Elsevier: 25-57.

- Mussatto, S. I., E. M. Machado, L. M. Carneiro & J. A. Teixeira (2012). "Sugars metabolism and ethanol production by different yeast strains from coffee industry wastes hydrolysates." *Applied Energy* **92**: 763-768.
- Mwaurah, P. W., S. Kumar, N. Kumar, A. K. Attkan, A. Panghal, V. K. Singh & M. K. Garg (2020). "Novel oil extraction technologies: Process conditions, quality parameters, and optimization." *Comprehensive reviews in food science and food safety* **19**(1): 3-20.
- Nguyen, N., H. Duong, H. Long, T. Nhi & D. Phat (2020). Effects of microwave extraction conditions on polyphenol content and antioxidant activity of pomelo extract (*Citrus maxima* (Burm.) Merr.). IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, IOP Publishing.
- Niglio, S., A. Procentese, M. E. Russo, G. Sannia & A. Marzocchella (2019). "Investigation of enzymatic hydrolysis of coffee silverskin aimed at the production of butanol and succinic acid by fermentative processes." *BioEnergy Research* **12**(2): 312-324.
- Niño-Medina, G., D. Muy-Rangel & V. Urías-Orona (2017). "Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*) and soybean (*Glycine max*) hulls: byproducts with potential use as a source of high value-added food products." *Waste and biomass valorization* **8**(4): 1199-1203.
- Niphadkar, S. S. & V. K. Rathod (2015). "Ultrasound-assisted three-phase partitioning of polyphenol oxidase from potato peel (*Solanum tuberosum*)." *Biotechnology progress* **31**(5): 1340-1347.
- Oliveira, D., P. Fox & J. A. O'Mahony (2019). "Byproducts from dairy processing." *Byproducts from Agriculture and Fisheries: Adding Value for Food, Feed, Pharma, and Fuels*: 57-106.
- Osorio, L. L. D. R., E. Flórez-López & C. D. Grande-Tovar (2021). "The potential of selected agri-food loss and waste to contribute to a circular economy: Applications in the food, cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries." *Molecules* **26**(2): 515.
- Ozkan, G., E. Karacabey, N. Arslan & N. Odabasi (2017). "Optimisation of microwave-assisted extraction of triterpenic acids from olive mill waste using response surface methodology." *Quality Assurance and Safety of Crops & Foods* **9**(2): 179-185.
- Özbek, H., D. K. Yanık, S. Fadiloğlu, H. K. Çavdar & F. Göğüş (2018). "Microwave-assisted extraction of non-polar compounds from pistachio hull and characterization of extracts." *Grasas y Aceites* **69**(3): e260-e260.
- Özbek, H. N., D. K. Yanık, S. Fadiloğlu & F. Göğüş (2020). "Optimization of microwave-assisted extraction of bioactive compounds from pistachio (*Pistacia vera* L.) hull." *Separation Science and Technology* **55**(2): 289-299.
- Park, J.-H., J.-H. Choe, H.-W. Kim, K.-E. Hwang, D.-H. Song, E.-J. Yeo, H.-Y. Kim, Y.-S. Choi, S.-H. Lee & C.-J. Kim (2013). "Effects of various extraction methods on quality characteristics of duck feet gelatin." *Food Science of Animal Resources* **33**(2): 162-169.
- Pereira, N. R., A. Marsaioli Jr & L. M. Ahrné (2007). "Effect of microwave power, air velocity and temperature on the final drying of osmotically dehydrated bananas." *Journal of Food Engineering* **81**(1): 79-87.
- Pérez-Serradilla, J. & M. L. De Castro (2011). "Microwave-assisted extraction of phenolic compounds from wine lees and spray-drying of the extract." *Food chemistry* **124**(4): 1652-1659.
- Racioppo, A., B. Speranza, D. Campaniello, M. Sinigaglia, M. R. Corbo & A. Bevilacqua (2021). "Fish loss/waste and low-value fish challenges: State of art, advances, and perspectives." *Foods* **10**(11): 2725.

- Rafiee, Z., S. Jafari, M. Alami & M. Khomeiri (2011). "Microwave-assisted extraction of phenolic compounds from olive leaves; a comparison with maceration." *J. Anim. Plant Sci* **21**(4): 738-745.
- Ramirez-Coronel, M. A., N. Marnet, V. K. Kolli, S. Roussos, S. Guyot & C. Augur (2004). "Characterization and estimation of proanthocyanidins and other phenolics in coffee pulp (*Coffea arabica*) by thiolysis– high-performance liquid chromatography." *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* **52**(5): 1344-1349.
- Rodriguez-Padron, D., D. Zhao, R. N. Garín Ortega, C. Len, A. M. Balu, A. García & R. Luque (2020). "Characterization and antioxidant activity of microwave-extracted phenolic compounds from biomass residues." *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering* **8**(3): 1513-1519.
- Rojasa, J. C., K. G. Ramírez, P. E. Velasquez, P. Acevedo & A. Santisa (2020). "Evaluation of bio-hydrogen production by dark fermentation from Cocoa waste mucilage." *CHEMICAL ENGINEERING* **79**.
- Rojo-Poveda, O., L. Barbosa-Pereira, G. Zeppa & C. Stévigny (2020). "Cocoa bean shell—a by-product with nutritional properties and biofunctional potential." *Nutrients* **12**(4): 1123.
- Routray, W. & V. Orsat (2012). "Microwave-assisted extraction of flavonoids: a review." *Food and Bioprocess Technology* **5**(2): 409-424.
- Ruiz-Aceituno, L., M. J. García-Sarrió, B. Alonso-Rodriguez, L. Ramos & M. L. Sanz (2016). "Extraction of bioactive carbohydrates from artichoke (*Cynara scolymus* L.) external bracts using microwave assisted extraction and pressurized liquid extraction." *Food chemistry* **196**: 1156-1162.
- SAMANLI, S., Ö. ÖNEY and K. GEVEZE (2017). "Mikroalga kurutmann kaolen numunesinin bilyalı değirmendeki özgül kırılma hızını artırıcı etkisi." *Journal of Science and Engineering* **19**(55).
- Santana, J. C., R. B. Gardim, P. F. Almeida, G. B. Borini, A. P. Quispe, S. A. Llanos, J. A. Heredia, S. Zamuner, F. M. Gamarra & T. M. Farias (2020). "Valorization of chicken feet by-product of the poultry industry: high qualities of gelatin and biofilm from extraction of collagen." *Polymers* **12**(3): 529.
- Sarmiento-Vásquez, Z., L. Vandenberghe, C. Rodrigues, V. O. A. Tanobe, O. Marín, G. V. de Melo Pereira, H. L. Ghislain Rogez, A. Góes-Neto & C. R. Soccol (2021). "Cocoa pod husk valorization: alkaline-enzymatic pre-treatment for propionic acid production." *Cellulose* **28**(7): 4009-4024.
- Sharma, S. K., S. Bansal, M. Mangal, A. K. Dixit, R. K. Gupta & A. Mangal (2016). "Utilization of food processing by-products as dietary, functional, and novel fiber: a review." *Critical reviews in food science and nutrition* **56**(10): 1647-1661.
- Silva, N. A. & S. R. Hiibel (2021). "Nutrient recovery of the hydrothermal carbonization aqueous product from dairy manure using membrane distillation." *Environmental Technology*: 1-10.
- Singh, R., K. Bhuyan, J. Banerjee, J. Muir and A. Arora (2017). "Hydrothermal and microwave assisted alkali pretreatment for fractionation of arecanut husk." *Industrial Crops and Products* **102**: 65-74.
- Tsubaki, S., M. Sakamoto & J.-i. Azuma (2010). "Microwave-assisted extraction of phenolic compounds from tea residues under autohydrolytic conditions." *Food Chemistry* **123**(4): 1255-1258.
- Uysal, B., F. Sozmen, O. Aktas, B. S. Oksal & E. O. Kose (2011). "Essential oil composition and antibacterial activity of the grapefruit (*Citrus Paradisi*. L) peel essential oils obtained by solvent-free microwave extraction: comparison with hydrodistillation." *International journal of food science & technology* **46**(7): 1455-1461.

- Uzun, B. B., E. Apaydin-Varol, F. Ateş, N. Özbay & A. E. Pütün (2010). "Synthetic fuel production from tea waste: characterisation of bio-oil and bio-char." *Fuel* **89**(1): 176-184.
- Vani, S., P. Binod, M. Kuttiraja, R. Sindhu, S. V. Sandhya, V. E. Preeti, R. K. Sukumaran & A. Pandey (2012). "Energy requirement for alkali assisted microwave and high pressure reactor pretreatments of cotton plant residue and its hydrolysis for fermentable sugar production for biofuel application." *Bioresource technology* **112**: 300-307.
- Venturi, F., S. Bartolini, C. Sanmartin, M. Orlando, I. Taglieri, M. Macaluso, M. Lucchesini, A. Trivellini, A. Zinnai & A. Mensuali (2019). "Potato peels as a source of novel green extracts suitable as antioxidant additives for fresh-cut fruits." *Applied Sciences* **9**(12): 2431.
- Vidal, A. R., L. P. Duarte, M. M. Schmidt, R. L. Cansian, I. A. Fernandes, R. de Oliveira Mello, I. M. Demiate & R. C. P. Dornelles (2020). "Extraction and characterization of collagen from sheep slaughter by-products." *Waste Management* **102**: 838-846.
- Wang, S., F. Chen, J. Wu, Z. Wang, X. Liao & X. Hu (2007). "Optimization of pectin extraction assisted by microwave from apple pomace using response surface methodology." *Journal of food engineering* **78**(2): 693-700.
- Wu, T., J. Yan, R. Liu, M. F. Marcone, H. A. Aisa & R. Tsao (2012). "Optimization of microwave-assisted extraction of phenolics from potato and its downstream waste using orthogonal array design." *Food Chemistry* **133**(4): 1292-1298.
- Xiaokang, W., J. G. Lyng, N. P. Brunton, L. Cody, J.-C. Jacquier, S. M. Harrison & K. Papoutsis (2020). "Monitoring the effect of different microwave extraction parameters on the recovery of polyphenols from shiitake mushrooms: Comparison with hot-water and organic-solvent extractions." *Biotechnology Reports* **27**: e00504.
- Yadav, D., L. Barbora, L. Rangan & P. Mahanta (2016). "Tea waste and food waste as a potential feedstock for biogas production." *Environmental Progress & Sustainable Energy* **35**(5): 1247-1253.
- Yanik, D. K. (2017). "Alternative to traditional olive pomace oil extraction systems: Microwave-assisted solvent extraction of oil from wet olive pomace." *LWT* **77**: 45-51.
- Yapo, B. M. & K. L. Koffi (2013). "Extraction and characterization of gelling and emulsifying pectin fractions from cacao pod husk." *Nature* **1**(4): 46-51.
- Yemiş, O. & G. Mazza (2012). "Optimization of furfural and 5-hydroxymethylfurfural production from wheat straw by a microwave-assisted process." *Bioresource technology* **109**: 215-223.
- Zhang, F., F. Zhu, B. Chen, E. Su, Y. Chen & F. Cao (2022). "Composition, bioactive substances, extraction technologies and the influences on characteristics of *Camellia oleifera* oil: a review." *Food Research International*: 111159.
- Zhang, Y. Y., T. H. Mu & M. Zhang (2013). "Optimisation of acid extraction of pectin from sweet potato residues by response surface methodology and its antiproliferation effect on cancer cells." *International journal of food science & technology* **48**(4): 778-785.
- Zhu, Z., R. Simister, S. Bird, S. J. McQueen-Mason, L. D. Gomez & D. J. Macquarrie (2015). "Microwave assisted acid and alkali pretreatment of *Miscanthus* biomass for biorefineries." *matrix* **10**: 16.